

Key Facts

Duration
42
Months

Budget
EU funding
8.999.820€

27 Partners
from
11 Countries

Consortium

Coordination

Project Coordinator
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Mission

Develop an Advanced AI-enabled Framework for Data Lifecycles Optimization & Data Spaces Integration

Objectives

Novel AI-enabled Tools for Sustainable & Human-factors-aware Data Creation in Diverse Dataspaces

Novel AI-boosted Data Brokers Matching Data Consumers with Data Providers across Different Sectors

Novel Data Processing & Analytics Services, Ensuring Data Privacy, Trustworthiness, Security, Re-use, & Disposal

Advanced Data Spaces Connectors for Extended Interoperability across Different Data Spaces

Use Cases

Outcomes will be evaluated in 6 Use Case Scenarios, focusing on 5 Diverse Data Spaces

Data Spaces

Mobility

Energy

Industry

Healthcare

Green Deal

